

INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

Thank you for agreeing to participate in our survey.

Before we start, we'd like for you to read the informed consent information below. Informed consent refers to the voluntary choice of an individual to participate in research based on an accurate and complete understanding of its purposes, procedures, risks, benefits, and alternatives. The survey will be completely anonymous and voluntary. We do not ask or identify any individuals who plan to participate in this survey. If you have any questions before completing this survey, please contact the investigators,*****.

Informed consent:

You must be 18 years or older to participate in this survey.

The purpose of this study is to understand what criteria software developers use to prioritize technical debt items in real software projects, that is, to decide when a technical debt item should be paid off. You are being asked to volunteer because you are a developer on a GitHub software project that has been chosen for this study and you will be asked to answer a questionnaire. This questionnaire is iterative, i.e. you will see it one step at a time, where each step has the same structure. At each step, you will see data about a technical debt item that we have found in your project, and you will see two questions about that item that we want you to answer. The first question is "When should the item be paid off?", which is a multiple choice question. The second is "Why? Explain your above choice.", in which we ask you to explain what criteria you used to decide the payment priority in the previous question. After answering both questions, you click the "Next" button. Then, a new technical debt item will be shown on the screen. After every ten technical debt items, the system will display a screen asking if you want to continue and answer about a few more items. If you want to keep going, answer Yes and you'll see more technical debt items. If you're ready to quit, answer No.

The survey may take about 2 minutes to complete each technical debt item. You may see and answer questions about as many technical debt items as you wish.

Your participation in this research study is voluntary and you are free to withdraw or discontinue participation at any time. If you withdraw from this research study, you will not be penalized in any

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INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES way for deciding to stop participating. The data collected for this study will be retained by the investigator and analyzed even if you choose to withdraw from the research. If you do choose to withdraw, the investigator may use your information up to the time you decide to withdraw.

There are no known risks involved in completing the survey. One benefit is that you may contribute to understanding how developers prioritize technical debt and to the development of an intelligent method of technical debt prioritization. At the end of the project, we will make available a technical debt prioritization tool and videos teaching how to manage technical debt using the tool.

Another benefit is you can compete for prizes. In order to compete for the prize you must accumulate at least 100 points. In case of a tie, a draw will be made using a random choice tool such as [The Random Choice Generator Online Tool](#).

For each question answered you get 10 (ten) points. The maximum number of points received for answering questions will be 1,000 (one thousand) points. You also may invite other project developers to answer questionnaire, too. For each question answered by your friend you will earn 5 (five) points. The number of points earned from replies from the referred friends is unlimited. At the end of the study the 3 participants who accumulate the most points will earn a reward that will be a gift card.

The prizes will be Amazon gift cards in the following amounts:

1. USD 50.00 (fifty dollars) for first place
2. USD 30.00 (thirty dollars) for second place
3. USD 20.00 (twenty dollars) for third place

We will attempt to notify winners by email up to 5 times, within two weeks after closing the questionnaire. They will be asked to respond by accepting the prize and to authorize (or not) the publication of their GitHub username as one of the winners on the questionnaire website. Only the usernames of developers who give permission will be published. For users who do not authorize, we will publish [private] instead of the username.

Any information learned and collected from this study in which you might be identified will remain confidential and will be disclosed ONLY if you give permission. The investigator (s) will attempt to

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INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH ACTIVITIES keep your personal information confidential. To help protect your confidentiality, the investigator(s) will not store the relationship between any answer and you. Besides that, around 70% of the questions will be about technical debt items in files that the participant has already contributed. The other 30% will be chosen at random from all technical debt items in the project. As the selected projects have three or more participants, this technique will allow you to anonymize the tracking of participant responses. This technique together with the data structure used ensures anonymity of answer. That is, it is not possible to identify which participant provided the answer. In addition, all the collected data will be stored in a PostgreSQL database. The database will be stored in a cloud Linux server. In this server there are codes to identify the participant. The file with the developer identification will be encrypted and stored in a local machine to avoid developer exposure. We need to store the complete information of the user to interview the most engaged developers to better understand the data provided.

Only the investigator and members of the research team will have access to these records. If information learned from this study is published, you will not be identified by name. By signing this form, however, you allow the research study investigator to make your records available to the ***Institutional Review Board (IRB) and regulatory agencies as required to do so by law.

The principal investigator(s), ***, offer to answer any and all questions regarding your participation in this research study. If you have any further questions, you can contact ***.

This study has been reviewed and approved by the *** Institutional Review Board (IRB). A representative of that Board, from the Office of Research Protections and Compliance, is available to discuss the review process or your rights as a research participant. Contact information of the Office is ***.

After reading the consent items, please proceed to the questionnaire on the next page. Click "Go to Questionnaire" to get started with the survey. If you'd like to leave the survey at any time, just click "Exit this survey".

I have been informed that I may download a copy of the consent document clicking [here](#).

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